

Figure 1.

Figure 1. PRISMA Flow Diagram related to Islamic Green Economy

Source Adopted from <http://prisma-statement.org/prismastatement/flowdiagram.aspx>

Figure 2. Islamic Green Economy-Related Research by the Year 2013-2023

Source Author

Figure 3. Research Related to Islamic Green Economy Based on Quartile

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Figure 4. Mapping of Research Themes Related to the Islamic Green Economy

Source Processed with VOSviewer